

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№9

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Elektron nashr. 337 sahifa.

E'lon qilishga 2025-yil 1-sentyabrda ruxsat etildi.

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldix'o'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golischeva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

- Salimov Okil Umrzokovich**, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilkhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridakhon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

Postdan xaridgacha: influenser va ilg'or veb-ilova (PWA – progressive web app)ning chakana sotuvga real ta'siri	14
Abdulaziz Madjidov	
Ta'lim xizmatlari bozori samaradorligini oshirishda ta'lim klasterlarining roli	22
Imamova Nilufar Asamutdinovna	
Korxonalar raqobatbardoshligini oshirishda marketingning tovar strategiyasidan foydalanish holati.....	29
Xidirov Sherzod Olimovich	
O'zbekistonda moliyaviy savodxonlikni institutsionallashtirish: NFIS, Finlit.uz va ta'lim islohotlari	34
Irgashev Anvar Farxodovich	
Moslashuvchan menejment tizimlarini yashil iqtisodiyotga integratsiyalash tasnifi	39
Umarov Bezzod Batirovich	
Qishloq xo'jaligida innovatsion marketing strategiyasini ishlab chiqish.....	43
Sheraliev Axror Sodiqovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida moliyaviy bank xizmatlarini rivojlantirishning tendensiyalari, undan samarali foydalanish imkoniyatlari va konseptual jihatlari	48
Roziqov Behzod Bahrom o'g'li	
Metallurgiya korxonalarida raqamli texnologiyalarni joriy etish chet el tajribasi	54
Abdullayeva Matluba Nematovna	
Исследование связи между восприятием изменения климата и внедрением устойчивых методов ведения сельского хозяйства в Узбекистане	59
Светлана Ражабова, Бахром Миркасимов	
Surxondaryo viloyati qishloq xo'jalik tarmog'ini barqaror rivojlantirishni iqtisodiy-ekologik modellari	68
Abdug'aniyev Otobek Allajonovich, Xo'jamqulov Bekzod Turdaliyevich	
Milliy iqtisodiyotda real sektor salmog'i va uning o'zgarish tendensiyalari	75
Mambetjanov Qahramon Qurbandurdievich, Isoilova Muhabbat Rustamjon qizi	
Qo'shilgan qiymatni soliqqa tortish uslubiyoti: xususiyatlari, vazifalari va muammolari	89
Xaitov Shuxrat Sharipboyevich	
Kognitiv yondashuv asosida tibbiyot oliy ta'lim muassasalari talabalari grammatik va diskursiv kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishning nazariy modeli va pedagogik texnologiyasi.....	94
Dadadjanova Feruza Muhammadjusupovna	
Transport tizimining rivojlanishi milliy iqtisodiy o'sishining asosi sifatida	98
Narziyev Umidjon Baxrillayevich	
Loyiha risklarini aniqlashda zamonaviy usullar va ularning samaradorligi.....	105
Marufhanov Davron Xasanovich	
Современные методы управления на железнодорожном транспорте в процессе трансформации системы.....	109
Кушакова Мамура Наримановна	
Финансовые механизмы и модели менеджмента в развитии устойчивой экономики транспортных компаний	115
Шарапова Гулчебра Рустамовна	
Kasbiy ta'limda o'quvchilarning raqamli kompetensiyasini shakllantirish va baholashning innovatsion yondashuvlari	120
Maxkamova Zuhra Tursunpulotovna	
Audit ishi sifati darajasini oshirish yo'nalishlari.....	124
Qushmatov Otaxon Qurbonaliyevich	

Erkin iqtisodiy zonalarda investitsiya loyihalarini moliyalashtirishning nazariy va amaliy asoslari.....	131
Yuldashev Baxtiyor Gayradjonovich	
Ko'chmas mulk qiymatini baholash va uning ekonometrik tahlili	135
Jaloliddinova Mohira Alisher qizi	
Современные тенденции и вызовы бюджетно-макроэкономической политики в Узбекистане	142
Хазраткулова Лола Нармуминовна	
Интеллектуал mulkda iqtisodiy mohiyat, mazmun hamda huquqiy jihat uyg'unligi	148
N.D.Maxmudova	
Axborot texnologiyalari asosida ta'limda loyiha boshqaruvida sun'iy intellekt va mashinali o'qitish imkoniyatlari	152
Xodjiyeva Durdona Abdurasolovna	
Концепция "Зеленого учета" и его значение для экономического развития.....	157
Умарова Зулайхо Турсуновна	
Iqtisodiyotning asosiy tarmoq va sohalariga kiritilgan investitsiyalarning joriy holati tahlili	166
Ismailova Kutlibeka Ulug'bek qizi	
O'zbekistonda yoshlar tashkiloti faoliyatini tashkil etishning o'ziga xos jihatlari va rivojlanish bosqichlari	172
Usmonov Adxamjon A'zamjonovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi maxsus iqtisodiy zonalarini investitsion holatini hududlar kesimida tahlili.....	178
Anvarxonov Abdulatifxon Jamshidxon o'g'li	
Kichik biznes va o'rta biznesni rivojlantirish orqali aholi farovonligini ta'minlash.....	184
Ahmedov Oybek Turgunpulatovich, Nurqulov Nurbek Sirojiddin o'g'li	
Fiskal siyosat instrumentlari orqali yashirin iqtisodiyotni qisqartirish va legallashtirish metodologiyasi.....	189
Ergasheva Malikaxon Avazxon qizi	
Fond bozorida savdo strategiyasi va uni amalga oshirishga yo'nalishlari.....	192
Soliyev Istam Ixtiyorovich	
Sanoat korxonalarini innovatsion rivojlantirishning asosiy tamoyillari	197
Yuldasheva Kamola Miraliyevna	
Iqtisodiy barqarorlikni ta'minlashda davlat boshqaruvi tizimining isloh qilinishi: Tajriba va istiqbollar.....	202
Mashrabaliyev Ibroximbek Mashrabaliyevich	
Iqtisodiyotning real sektorida investitsion loyihalarni moliyalashtirish amaliyoti.....	209
Qosimova Lola Sultanovna	
Sanoat mahsulotlari eksportida logistika zanjirining uzluksizligini ta'minlash: nazariy asoslar va amaliy yondashuvlar.....	217
Kurbonova Ma'mura Abdulkarim qizi	
Soliq ma'murchiligiga zamonaviy texnologiyalarini joriy etish orqali qo'shilgan qiymat soliq ma'murchiligi bazasini kengaytirish yo'llari	222
Raxmonqulov Umidjon Rustam o'g'li	
Инновационные подходы к созданию проблемно-ориентированной системы прогнозирования, оптимизации и управления отраслями региональной экономики (жилищное строительство)	231
Далиев Ахтам Шарафутдинович	
Tovar-moddiy resurslar harakati samaradorligini oshirishda UZEX faoliyatining joriy holatini baholash.....	238
Sherzod Xolmurodovich Pardayev, Mamatkulov Farrux Gulomjon o'g'li	
Sog'liqni saqlash tizimida tadbirkorlik faoliyatining turlari	244
Solikhova Dildora Alisher qizi	

“O‘ztemiryo‘lyo‘lovchi” ajning asisiy faoliyatini samaradorligini oshirishda autsorsing xizmatini joriy etish strategik asoslari	250
Kaxarova Nilufar Yerkinjonovna	
Mintaqani kompleks rivojlantirishning metodologik asoslari va ustuvor yo‘nalishlari.....	256
Jumayeva Zulfiya Qayumovna	
Sog‘liqni saqlash tashkilotarida xarajatlar samaradorligini ta‘minlash masalalari	260
Raximova Maftuna Axmadjon qizi	
Aksiyadorlik jamiyatlarida sof foydani taqsimlash bilan bog‘liq bo‘lgan soliq solish masalalari.....	264
Suyunov Otabek Shuxrat o‘g‘li	
Mahalla instituti asosida kambag‘allikni qisqartirishda targetlash mexanizmlarining samaradorligi.....	269
Baratov J.N.	
O‘zbekiston qonunchiligida raqamli transformatsiya jarayonida elektron to‘lov kartalarini soxtalashtirishni jinoyatlashtirish.....	276
Maxsadalievna Maftuna Toxir qizi	
Mamlakatimizda intellektual xizmatlar bozorini rivojlantirish masalalari.....	281
Miyassarov Davron Abdurashid o‘g‘li	
Validation of the dutch eating behaviour questionnaire (DEBQ) in a sample of uzbek women.....	285
Khursana Usmanova, Dr Muhammad Bilal, Dilafuz Qo‘chqorova	
Iqtisodiy xavfsizlik tizimlarini o‘ziga xos jihatlari	295
Nabiyev Bezxod Shavkatovich, Bayboboeva Firuza Nabijonovna	
Davlat qarz siyosatini optimallashtirishda islomiy moliya instrumentlarining qo‘llanish imkoniyatlarini kengaytirish yo‘nalishlari	299
Tilabov Nasrulla Tashmurotovich	
Роль институциональных структур фондового рынка в обеспечении финансовой стабильности.....	305
Камилова Севара Анваровна	
The Impact of Digitalization on the Management System in the Entrepreneurial Environment of Uzbekistan.....	309
Ibragimova Saida Ilkhomovna	
China’s Investment Strategy in Uzbekistan: Sectoral Trends and Strategic Implications (2013–2024).....	313
Maftuna Nuriddinova	
Qo‘shilgan qiymat solig‘i tushunchasi va uning iqtisodiy mohiyati	319
Eshkarayev Bobir Chariyevich	
Raqamli boshqaruvning afzalliklari va uni rivojlantirish istiqbollari	324
Xolbayeva Marg‘uba Qazoqboyevna	
Korporativ boshqaruvning nazariy asoslari: O‘zbekistonda qo‘llanish imkoniyatlari.....	328
Jumayeva Guzal Sherxon qizi	
Audit organizations in Uzbekistan	332
Razzaqov Jasur Xamraboevich, Yaqubov Matrasul Mavlonberdiyevich, Sabirova Nodira Komil qizi	

AUDIT ORGANIZATIONS IN UZBEKISTAN

Razzaqov Jasur Xamraboевич

Tashkent State Agrarian University,
Head of the Department of
Accounting, Analysis and Audit, DSc

Yaqubov Matrasul Mavlonberdiyevich

BANKING AND FINANCE ACADEMY,
Head of the Department of
Accounting and Auditing, PhD

Sabirova Nodira Komil qizi

Tashkent State Agrarian University,
teacher of the Department of
Accounting, Analysis and Audit, Msc

Abstract: As Uzbekistan shifts to a market economy, the audit industry has experienced substantial change. Uzbekistan has been working to create a legal framework to create a strong audit system that complies with international standards ever since gaining independence in 1991. In order to encourage accountability, openness, and sound governance in the nation's economic institutions, audit organizations—both public and private—have been established. Given its significance in promoting an open and responsible economic system, this article offers a concise summary of the audit organization structure, legal framework, and major issues in Uzbekistan.

Key words: Audit, International Standards of Audit, National Auditing Standards, Licensing, compliance, setting standards, financial reporting, tax advisory, financial services for SMEs.

Annotatsiya: O'zbekiston bozor iqtisodiyotiga o'tayotgan bir paytda auditorlik sohasida ham jiddiy o'zgarishlar ro'y berdi. O'zbekiston 1991-yilda mustaqillikka erishganidan buyon xalqaro standartlarga javob beradigan kuchli audit tizimini yaratish bo'yicha qonunchilik bazasini yaratish ustida ishlamoqda. Mamlakatning iqtisodiy institutlarida, auditorlik tashkilotlarida – ham davlat, ham auditorlik tashkilotlarida hisobdorlik, ochiqlik va ishonchli boshqaruvni rag'batlantirish maqsadida. xususi - tashkil etilgan. Ochiq va mas'uliyatli iqtisodiy tizimni targ'ib qilishdagi ahamiyatini inobatga olgan holda, ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda auditorlik tashkiloti tuzilmasi, qonunchilik bazasi va asosiy masalalari haqida qisqacha ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Audit, Xalqaro audit standartlari, Milliy audit standartlari, Litsenziyalash, standartlarni belgilash, moliyaviy hisobot, soliq maslahati, SME uchun moliyaviy xizmatlar.

Аннотация: По мере перехода Узбекистана к рыночной экономике в сфере аудита произошли существенные изменения. Узбекистан работает над созданием правовой базы для создания сильной системы аудита, соответствующей международным стандартам, с момента обретения независимости в 1991 году. В целях поощрения подотчетности, открытости и рационального управления в экономических институтах страны, аудиторские организации - как государственные, так и частные — установлены. Учитывая его значение в продвижении открытой и ответственной экономической системы, в настоящей статье предлагается краткое изложение структуры аудиторской организации, правовой базы и основных проблем в Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: Аудит, Международные стандарты аудита, Национальные стандарты аудита, Лицензирование, установление стандартов, финансовая отчетность, налоговое консультирование, финансовые услуги для МСП.

INTRODUCTION

Since the emergence of international commercial contacts and the start of market changes, the subject of whether an audit is necessary in Uzbekistan has been raised.

In order to draw in foreign investment, promises of return were necessary, necessitating an unbiased evaluation of the operations of entrepreneurial organizations. An impartial audit is typically the best method

for obtaining accurate information. As a result, audits are now objectively necessary, and without them, the government is unable to regulate the deliberate use of public monies.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

With the adoption of the “On Audit Activity” Law in 1992, audit activity got underway in Uzbekistan. International Auditing Standards (ISA) served as the foundation for the development of National Auditing Standards (NAS). International Auditing Standards (ISA) served as the foundation for the development of National Auditing Standards (NAS). The provisions of the NAS are out of current in comparison to the ISA since the ISA is subject to periodic revisions. NAS are one of the components that regulate audit activities and provide as the foundation for the creation of audit companies’ internal standards and auditing technique. In Uzbekistan, a progressive reform of auditing operations is ongoing. The Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Chamber of Auditors of Uzbekistan, and the National Association of Accountants and Auditors are the primary reformers of audit work. On 10 November 2020, a plenary session was conducted at the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan to consider the second reading of the bill of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Auditing Activities”. This draft law was reportedly created to guarantee the execution of the Republic of Uzbekistan President PP-3946 of September 19, 2018, decision approving the “Action Plan for the further development of audit activities in the Republic of Uzbekistan.” Deputies from the Oliy Majlis’ Legislative Chamber, the draft law’s creators, leaders and staff of public audit groups, a consortium of national specialists, and audit organizations were present during the debate. In order to provide a single normative legal instrument that allows for the adoption of several standards intended to ensure auditing independence, the draft legislation was created to organize and harmonize the several documents governing auditing. Specifically, it stipulates that audit operations must only be carried out in accordance with international auditing standards, streamlines the process, and grants the authority to do an audit. Furthermore, the development of an efficient method to raise auditor credentials is proposed. Most significantly, the process for granting auditing licenses will no longer be used, and instead a streamlined registry of auditors and audit firms will be applied in order to guarantee the freedom of audit activities. This kind of activity will be further developed by eliminating the requirement for an audit organization’s minimum permitted capital and by allowing audits to be conducted inside the same economic entity for up to seven years in a row. On the other hand, republican public associations of auditors and a specially authorized state body exercise external control over the quality of their work without meddling in the financial and economic operations of audit organizations in order to guarantee and enhance the quality of audit services. Additionally, it calls for conducting audit operations exclusively in accordance with international audit standards and raising the required minimum number of auditors in an audit organization from the present two to at least four, both of which will enhance the caliber of auditing.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the article, the authors used scientific abstraction, systematic analysis, and comparative comparison methods.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Principal duties and responsibilities of the Chamber Assistance in formulating the primary audit development directions throughout the Republic of Uzbekistan based on a single approach. Coordination of audit activities, formation of standing commissions, exceptional commissions and working groups on issues of professional activity of auditors. to carry out market research on audit services in order to help satisfy the demand for these services. conducting conferences and seminars, publishing information and methodological resources, and researching, aggregating, and sharing best audit practices. to give audit companies and auditors advice on how to carry out their responsibilities. To insure professional risks for both individual auditors and audit companies. Draft suggestions and ideas for the advancement of auditing, and take the lead on legislation in this regard.

The program and method for holding qualifying exams for the right to get an auditor’s certificate must be developed and approved by the Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan as well as other interested entities. collaboration and communication with other governmental agencies, as well as auditing and accounting firms both domestically and internationally. In order to hold auditors accountable for any infractions, the Chamber may, if needed, provide recommendations to the audit organization on the Code of Professional Ethics of Auditors’ approval and the assessment of claims against their actions. creates audit templates and report formats according to international standards.

Table 2

Audit Organization	Type	Key Services
Chamber of Auditors of Uzbekistan	Regulatory Body	Licensing, compliance, setting standards
Association of Professional Accountants and Auditors of Uzbekistan (APAAU)	Professional Association	Certification, training, professional development
PwC Uzbekistan	International Audit Firm	Audit, consulting, tax
KPMG Uzbekistan	International Audit Firm	Audit, advisory, corporate governance
Deloitte Uzbekistan	International Audit Firm	Audit, tax, consulting, risk advisory
Ernst & Young (EY) Uzbekistan	International Audit Firm	Audit, tax, advisory
Grant Thornton Uzbekistan	International Audit Firm	Audit, tax advisory, business consulting
Crowe Horwath Uzbekistan	International Audit Firm	Audit, risk management, consulting
Baker Tilly Uzbekistan	International Audit Firm	Audit, financial reporting, tax advisory
Bashan Audit	Local Audit Firm	Audit, financial services for SMEs
UHY Tashkent Audit	Local Audit Firm (UHY Network)	Audit, tax, consulting
Ministry of Finance of Uzbekistan	Governmental Body	Setting national audit standards, regulation
State Tax Committee of Uzbekistan	Governmental Body	Tax audit regulation, tax compliance monitoring

This table provides a summary of key organizations involved in audit practices in Uzbekistan.

Figure 1

The Uzbekistan Respublikasi Auditorlar Palatasi, or Chamber of Auditors, Function: This is Uzbekistan’s primary regulating agency for auditing activities. The Chamber makes sure that auditing companies abide by the rules and national requirements. Additionally, it strives to elevate the nation’s audit profession.

Functions include licensing audit companies, establishing professional standards, planning auditor training and education programs, and ensuring adherence to national audit legislation.

2. Uzbekistan's Association of Professional Accountants and Auditors (APAAU)

Function: An organization for professionals that assists Uzbek accountants and auditors. It supports the interests of auditors and accountants, offers certification, and encourages professional growth.

Functions include standard-setting in accordance with worldwide best practices, auditor certification, training, and professional development.

3. Uzbekistan's Big Four Audit Firms

Uzbekistan is home to a number of foreign auditing organizations, including the Big Four:

One of the top international audit companies, PwC Uzbekistan (PricewaterhouseCoopers) offers audit, consulting, and tax services in Uzbekistan.

KPMG Uzbekistan: Provides audit and consultancy services in Uzbekistan with an emphasis on banking, corporate governance, and financial services.

Deloitte Uzbekistan: Provides audit, tax, consultancy, and risk management services throughout the nation.

Ernst & Young (EY) Uzbekistan: Offers audit, tax, and consulting services; has experience in oil and gas, manufacturing, and banking, among other areas.

4. The role of Grant Thornton Uzbekistan: This international auditing and consulting company is present in Uzbekistan. For businesses operating in the area, it provides services including business consultation, tax advising, and auditing.

5. Crowe Horwath Uzbekistan Role: Crowe Horwath is a worldwide network of audit companies with a presence in Uzbekistan. It offers consultancy, risk management, and auditing services to companies across many industries.

6. Baker Tilly Uzbekistan Role: Part of the worldwide network of accounting and consulting organizations, Baker Tilly International. In Uzbekistan, it provides tax advising, financial reporting, and auditing services.

7. Regional Accounting Firms

Bashan Audit is a local company that provides financial services and audits to small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) in Uzbekistan.

UHY Tashkent Audit: A part of the global UHY network, offering tax, consulting, and auditing services.

8. The Uzbek Ministry of Finance

Function: The Ministry of Finance is in charge of Uzbekistan's accounting and auditing regulations. It guarantees adherence to rules governing financial reporting and audits and establishes national standards.

9. The Uzbek State Tax Committee

Participates in the regulation and oversight of audits pertaining to taxes. It frequently collaborates with audit organizations to make sure businesses abide by the tax regulations in Uzbekistan.

In the context of Uzbekistan's expanding economy, these organizations are essential in advancing financial integrity, accountability, and transparency.

Figure 2

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Audit organizations in Uzbekistan play a vital role in ensuring financial transparency, accountability, and compliance with national and international standards. Over the past decade, the country has made significant strides in reforming its auditing sector, aligning it with global practices and enhancing regulatory oversight. The adoption of International Standards on Auditing (ISA), the development of professional certification systems, and the strengthening of institutional frameworks have all contributed to improving audit quality. However, further efforts are needed to increase the independence of audit firms, enhance professional competencies, and ensure the consistent application of standards across both public and private sectors.

REFERENCE:

1. Audit / Ed. M. M. Tulakhodzhaeva, T. I. Dzhuraeva, F. G. Gulyamova. - Tashkent: TSEU, 2013. 8. Sanaev N., Narziev R. Audit. -T.: Shark, 2001(Accessed: 1 September 2025)
2. Audit and assurance (no date) KPMG. Available at: <https://kpmg.com/uz/ru/home/services/audit.html> (Accessed: 1 September 2025).
3. Member (no date) IFAC. Available at: <https://www.ifac.org/about-ifac/membership/members/chamber-auditors-uzbekistan> (Accessed: 1 September 2025).
4. Karimov I. A. Global financial and economic crisis, ways and measures to overcome it in the conditions of Uzbekistan. -T.: Uzbekistan, 2009. 56 p. (Accessed: 1 September 2025)
5. Nematullah, K. (2020) Stages of implementation and problems of implementation of international auditing standards in Uzbekistan, International Academy Journal Web of Scholar. Available at: https://doi.org/10.31435/rsglobal_wos/31012020/6882 (Accessed: 1 September 2025).
6. On audit activity (no date) On Audit Activity - 'Adilet' LIS. Available at: <https://adilet.zan.kz/eng/docs/Z980000304> (Accessed: 1 September 2025)
7. The new edition of the Law of Uzbekistan "On audit activity" was approved by the deputies (uzdaily.uz) Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Auditing". May 26, 2000(Accessed: 13 1 September 2025)
8. The Republic of Uzbekistan accounting and Auditing. Available at: <https://cfr.worldbank.org/sites/default/files/2019-11/693860ROSC0box01C00UZ0A0AROSC0final.pdf> (Accessed: 1 September 2025).

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 9

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin.
Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>
